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Очилов Улугбек Усманович

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Шавази Наргиз Нуралиевна

DSc, доцент, заведующая кафедрой акушерства и гинекологии N 3 СамГМУ. <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7859-9955>

Юлдашев Равшан Захидович

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Теребаев Билим Алдамуратович

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Ибрагимова Малика Худайбергатовна

доктор медицинских наук, профессор Ташкентского государственного стоматологического института **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-9235-1742

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доктор медицинских наук, профессор кафедры онкологии Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета **ORCID ID:** 0000-0001-5272-5503

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Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute,
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ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5409-4327.*

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*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor of
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ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2442-1523*

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ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9235-1742*

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ORCID: 0009-0004-7661-9253.*

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KHAMRAEV Abror Asrarovich

DSc, professor

TURSUNOVA Minavara Ulugbekovna

PhD, Associate Professor

ABDULLAEV Ulugbek Sayfullaevich

PhD

Tashkent Medical Academy, Republic of Uzbekistan

MOLECULAR-GENETIC ASPECTS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF CHRONIC PANCREATITIS OF DIFFERENT GENESIS

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ANNOTATION

Abstract: Chronic pancreatitis (CP) is a progressive inflammatory disease of the pancreas characterized by a prolonged course and fibrosis development, which can lead to organ dysfunction. Despite significant advancements in medicine, the diagnosis and treatment of chronic pancreatitis remains a complex and multifaceted task. This is due to numerous factors, such as the diversity of etiological factors, late diagnosis of the disease, and the lack of universal treatment methods. One of the most important aspects in understanding the pathogenesis of chronic pancreatitis is the molecular-genetic approach. Genetic predisposition plays a key role in the development of the disease, and in recent decades, several genes have been identified that can contribute to the development of CP of various origins.

Keywords: chronic pancreatitis, molecular genetic aspects.

XAMRAYEV Abror Asrarovich

t.f.d., professor

TURSUNOVA Minavara Ulug'bekovna

t.f.n. katta o'qituvchi

ABDULLAYEV Ulug'bek Sayfullayevich

t.f.n.

Toshkent tibbiyot akademiyasi

TURLI GENEZLI SURUNKALI PANKREATIT RIVOJLANISHINING MOLEKULYAR-GENETIK JIHATLARI

ANNOTATSIYA

Surunkali pankreatit (SP) oshqozon osti bezining progressiv yallig‘lanish kasalligi bo‘lib, uzoq muddatli kechishi va fibroz rivojlanishi bilan tavsiflanadi, bu esa a‘zo funksiyasining buzilishiga olib kelishi mumkin. Tibbiyotdagi sezilarli yutuqlarga qaramay, surunkali pankreatitni tashxislash va davolash murakkab va ko‘p qirrali vazifa bo‘lib qolmoqda. Bu ko‘plab omillar bilan bog‘liq, masalan, etiologik omillarning xilma-xilligi, kasallikning kech tashxisi va universal davolash usullarining yo‘qligi. Surunkali pankreatitning patogenezini tushunishning eng muhim jihatlaridan biri molekulyar genetik yondashuvdir. Kasallikning rivojlanishida genetik moyillik asosiy rol o‘ynaydi va so‘nggi o‘n yilliklarda turli xil genezli SP rivojlanishiga hissa qo‘shishi mumkin bo‘lgan bir nechta genlar aniqlandi.

Kalit so‘zlar: surunkali pankreatit, molekulyar-genetik jihatlar.

ХАМРАЕВ Аброр Асрарович

д.м.н., профессор

ТУРСУНОВА Минавара Улугбековна

к.м.н., старший преподаватель

АБДУЛЛАЕВ Улугбек Сайфуллаевич

к.м.н., ассистент

Ташкентская медицинская академия, Республика Узбекистан

МОЛЕКУЛЯРНО-ГЕНЕТИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ХРОНИЧЕСКОГО ПАНКРЕАТИТА РАЗЛИЧНОГО ГЕНЕЗА

АННОТАЦИЯ

Хронический панкреатит (ХП) представляет собой прогрессирующее воспалительное заболевание поджелудочной железы, характеризующееся длительным течением и развитием фиброза, что может привести к нарушению функции органа. Несмотря на значительный прогресс в медицине, диагностика и лечение хронического панкреатита остаются сложными и многогранными задачами. Это связано с множеством факторов, таких как разнообразие этиологических факторов, поздняя диагностика заболевания и отсутствие универсальных методов терапии. Одним из важнейших аспектов в понимании патогенеза хронического панкреатита является молекулярно-генетический подход. Генетическая предрасположенность играет ключевую роль в развитии заболевания, и в последние десятилетия было выявлено несколько генов, которые могут способствовать развитию ХП различного генеза.

Ключевые слова: хронический панкреатит, молекулярно генетические аспекты.

In European countries, chronic pancreatitis (CP) is caused by alcohol misuse in at least 80% of cases. A significant number is of unknown origin (so-called “idiopathic CP”), whereas other etiologies are rare. A very rare cause of CP, hereditary chronic pancreatitis, has been extensively investigated during the last years. These efforts markedly extended our knowledge of the pathogenesis of chronic pancreatitis. In this summary of a lecture held at the Pancreas Symposium of the Polish Society of Gastroenterology hold in Pułtusk, Poland, in June 2003, we address the clinical aspects of hereditary pancreatitis and point to recent news regarding the genetic background of chronic pancreatitis. During the last years, some comprehensive reviews have been published and are suggested for further reading [1].

Clinical characteristics of Hereditary pancreatitis. The classical clinical attribute of hereditary pancreatitis (HP) is characterized by recurrent episodes of acute pancreatitis or a priori chronic pancreatitis in several members of one family. Typically, the pattern of affected family members exhibits an autosomal dominant trait in the absence of other causes of chronic pancreatitis [3], but only 70–80% of obligate carriers are affected. HP may be symptomatic in infants less than one year old, but the median age of onset is 10–13 years. An analysis of clinical characteristics in 106 patients from 27 HP families revealed bimodal modus of onset at 1–6 years and 18–24 years of age; the severity of chronic pancreatitis was mild in most of the affected patients [2].

Medical and surgical treatment. The conservative treatment of HP does not differ from that of common forms of chronic pancreatitis. Several case reports, but few systematic investigations, exist in surgical HP treatment. Chronic pain in the presence of a persistent dilatation of the main pancreatic duct is the widely accepted indication for surgery in HP patients. The surgical technique of choice is a longitudinal pancreatojejunostomy (Partington-Rochelle procedure) with good early results. In patients without pancreatic duct dilation, however, surgery seems not to be beneficial for the further course of pancreatitis nor for quality of life [4]. Surgical interventions should be discussed with caution in children, as periods of only a few or even no symptoms frequently extend into adulthood. For these reasons, a decision to wait and see is superior to early surgery in pediatric HP patients. In adults, surgical decisions based on the guidelines for patients with chronic pancreatitis of more common etiology are generally as effective in patients with HP as in patients with chronic pancreatitis of other etiology [6]

Hereditary pancreatitis and pancreatic cancer HP patients have a more than 50-fold increased risk of pancreatic ductal cancer in comparison with expected pancreatic cancers in the general population [5]. The reduction of independent risk factors, i.e. smoking, is up to now the only preventive strategy. No screening protocol of proven efficiency exists for the early detection of pancreatic cancer in HP patients. An international consensus conference recommended that HP patients >40 years should be screened yearly by minimally invasive imaging to detect pancreatic cancer in a potentially curable state [8]. In patients suspected of having HP, a clear diagnosis or exclusion of HP is important not only to screen them from increased risk of pancreatic cancer. Neither clinical characteristics nor laboratory or radiological investigations are able to distinguish between HP and chronic pancreatitis of another etiology. A careful pedigree analysis is necessary to support the suspicion of the presence of HP or not. Even this approach, however, does not confirm the diagnosis of HP in many patients.

Trypsinogen mutations in HP. Since its first description in 1952, the phenomenon of early onset pancreatitis in many members of one family remained enigmatic until molecular techniques became available. The identification of the first HP-associated mutation in the cationic trypsinogen gene provided a breakthrough in our understanding of the pathogenesis of this and other forms of acute and chronic pancreatitis. A R122H mutation was reported in all affected members of five families with HP [7]. Several different mutations, such as the N29I and the A16V mutations in this same gene, have been subsequently found in a large number of investigated families [10]. In recent years, in vitro biochemical experiments using recombinant trypsinogen preparations have provided the most penetrating insight into the pathogenesis of genetically determined chronic pancreatitis, while the development of complementary cell biological or transgenic approaches have been lagging. To date, eight mutations have been studied with recombinant cationic trypsinogen or using synthetic peptides [9]. The mutations D22G, K23R, N29I, N29T, R122H, and R122C increase autoactivation of cationic trypsinogen. Furthermore, the mutations N29T, R122H, and R122C stabilize cationic trypsin against autolysis, whereas the mutations D22G, K23R, and N29I have no such effect [11]. The mutation R122H eliminates the autolytic cleavage site Arg122 [12]. The mutations D22G and K23R inhibit activation by cathepsin B [14], while mutations N29T, N29I, and R122H have no such effect [13]. All these actions of mutant trypsinogens could disrupt the balance of pancreatic protease-

antiprotease equilibrium with a surplus of intracellular protease activity. Via a different pathway, the E79K mutation of the cationic trypsin leads to an enhanced transactivation of anionic trypsinogen [15]. It is assumed that the resulting imbalance may initiate a further activation of trypsinogen and other pancreatic zymogens, with subsequent “autodigestion” of the pancreas. Indirect evidence for this concept came from a recent study by Chen and colleagues. In an alcoholic person without pancreatitis, they identified a stop codon mutation in exon 2. This is certainly a “loss of function” mutation. As this variant is not associated with chronic pancreatitis, the authors argue that a “loss of function” trypsin may be a protective factor against chronic pancreatitis in combination with an exogenous risk factor such as chronic alcoholism [16]. These theories are in accordance with the widely accepted hypothesis that intrapancreatic activation of trypsinogen Review Article Med Sci Monit, 2004; 10(12): RA325-328 RA326 to trypsin is thought to be an important event in the initiation of acute pancreatitis [18]. Future research will determine whether or not any of these mutation-specific mechanisms contribute to pancreatitis development or whether they simply represent biochemical epiphenomena unrelated to disease pathogenesis. **SPINK1 MUTATIONS IN Chronic pancreatitis** **SPINK1** (a serine protease inhibitor, Kazal type 1), also known as pancreatic secretory trypsin inhibitor (PSTI), is synthesized in the acinar cell and has the capacity to inhibit about 20% of total potential trypsin activity in the pancreas. Genetic variants of this natural intrapancreatic trypsin antagonist may have marked implications for other forms of chronic pancreatitis not involving specific mutations in the trypsinogen gene. After the first description of an N34S mutation in 18 out of 96 unrelated children and adolescents with idiopathic chronic pancreatitis [17], several groups have confirmed that this mutation is associated with chronic idiopathic pancreatitis in over 20% of patients. The N34S mutation was furthermore found in 6% of patients with chronic alcoholic pancreatitis. The most interesting finding is its prevalence in up to 50% of patients with different forms of tropical pancreatitis. Our understanding of tropical pancreatitis was markedly challenged by this finding, as tropical pancreatitis has hitherto been ascribed to malnutrition alone. At present, although SPINK1 mutations seem to be important in understanding the pathogenesis of chronic pancreatitis in general, investigations to define their role in different forms of pancreatitis are ongoing. Initially, enhanced intrapancreatic protease activity caused by a reduction in pancreatic autoproteolytic SPINK1 activity has been hypothesized as the crucial step for the initiation of pancreatitis in the affected patients [20]. A first set of in vitro studies with mutated SPINK1 molecules has demonstrated, however, no effect of the N34S mutation on the autoproteolytic potential of SPINK1. The authors argue that other effects, such as splice variations due to cosegregating intron mutations, may be the decisive pathogenetic step. Future research has to address this concept [19].

CFTR mutations in chronic pancreatitis. The autosomal recessive cystic fibrosis syndrome is the most common inherited lethal metabolic disorder. It is caused by mutations in the gene coding for the cystic fibrosis transmembrane conductance regulator (CFTR). Chronic pancreatitis represents a variable part of this syndrome. Several groups have reported an increased prevalence of CFTR mutations in patients with chronic pancreatitis. Studying disease-associated CFTR mutations is hampered by the current practical impossibility of investigating the complete genomic sequence of the CFTR gene in a large, representative population of patients, as this gene codes for 1480 amino acids. More than 1000 sequence variants are now known to exist (www.genet.sickkids.on.ca/cftr). A drawback of the current routine screening procedures is that only 20 to 40 frequent, population-specific CFTR mutations are now being screened [11]. Only a few studies have analyzed the complete CFTR coding sequence and PRSS1 and SPINK1 genes in patients with chronic pancreatitis. In two recent studies, 25% to 30% carried at least one CFTR mutation, and several patients were compound-heterozygous for different CFTR mutations or were trans-heterozygous for a CFTR mutation and a mutation in SPINK1 or cationic trypsinogen.

Pancreatitis associated mutations in Poland and eastern Europe. Within our cohort of more than one thousand patients whose blood samples were referred for the investigation of genetic

risk factors of chronic pancreatitis, we included only 27 patients from Poland. In three patients from one Polish HP family we detected the R122H mutation of the cationic trypsinogen. One other patient with putative idiopathic pancreatitis carried the SPINK1 mutation N34S, whereas the other 23 patients carried wild-type sequences. These very limited results are in line with the findings in Western Europe, North America, and in Japan. Little is known about the distribution of pancreatitis-associated mutation in other East European countries. In the Ukraine we detected an exceptional cationic trypsinogen variant in one well-characterized family with hereditary pancreatitis, which is the only known family with HP in the Ukraine. This D22G mutation alters the amino acid sequence adjacent to the cleavage site of the trypsinogen activation peptide. The tryptic cleavage of synthetic N-terminal peptides, covering the activation site, revealed that the cleavage at the trypsinogen activation site of the D22G peptide was markedly facilitated compared with the wildtype peptide [20]. Furthermore, this mutation seems to be completely resistant to cathepsin B-mediated trypsinogen activation [1]. Our findings suggest that the activation peptide in the trypsinogen variant D22G may be released more easily than in the wild-type proenzyme, which could lead to pancreatitis by a protease surplus in the pancreatic protease antiprotease system. In a recent paper by Chen et al, which first investigated recombinant expressed D22G trypsinogen as well as the earlier detected K23R and a novel D19A mutation within the activation peptide, it was found that all three of these mutations significantly increased autoactivation of cationic trypsinogen, particularly in the two mutations D22G and K23R, which are closer to the trypsinogen activation site K23-I24 than is D19A [6]. The question needs to be answered whether the D22G variant is frequent in the East of Europe or whether its impact is limited to the reported family. The latter is reasonable, as most of the genetic variants of the reported genes have been reported in just one patient or some members of one family. Thus, it is unclear whether they cause hereditary or idiopathic pancreatitis or whether they are associated to pancreatitis by chance. Today, 23 PRSS1 and 31 SPINK1 variants have been published.

Conclusions. In conclusion, recent genetic findings in chronic pancreatitis represent breakthroughs in our understanding of the pathogenesis of pancreatic diseases. The identification of a genetic predisposition or actual genetic cause of hereditary, Med SciMonit, 2004; 10(12): RA325-328 Teich N et al – Genetic aspects of chronic pancreatitis RA327 RA idiopathic, and alcoholic chronic pancreatitis, followed by functional and pharmacological studies, offers the potential to understand their pathogenesis and to develop urgently needed, but as yet unavailable, preventive and therapeutic strategies. The underlying genetic defect is still unknown in more than 50% of all HP families. Future research will elucidate other high-risk genes, which will further expand our knowledge of the hereditary and other forms of chronic pancreatitis as well as their pathogenesis.

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